

RIPARIAN FLORA OF THAMIRAPARANI RIVER IN KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA

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Abstract:

Riparian flora is an expressed survey to analyze marginal vegetation of river zones. The present study was conducted in Thamiraparani river of Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, India. Result of the current study showed a total of, 720 species of angiosperms belonging to 449 genera under 126 families of these 76.5% were dicots and 23.5% of monocots were recorded. Habitually 30.4% herbs, 26.7% trees, 15.7% shrubs, 6.9% climbing shrubs, 5.2% perennial herbs, 3.3% annual herbs, 2% twining herbs, 1.7% twining shrubs, 1.6% aquatic herbs, 1.3% climbing herbs, 0.6% rhizomatous herbs, 0.7% marshy herbs, 0.7% tuberous herbs, 0.6% lianas, 0.4% tuberous climbing herbs, 0.4% straggling shrubs, 0.3% climbers, 0.3% climbing palms, 0.3% prostrate herbs, climbing shrub, creeping herb, epiphytic herb, parasitic shrub and parasitic twining herb were 0.1%. Poaceae is the dominant family followed by Fabaceae, Acanthaceae and Euphorbiaceae. 114 plant species were conserved under RET category, 568 species occurred commonly 98 species were exotic. Most of the plants were widely used as medicinals. Anthropogenic activities act as a barrier biodiversity.

Key Words: Angiosperm, Anthropogenic, Flora, Kanyakumari, Riparian & Tamiraparni

Introduction:

“Riparian” word derived from the Latin word ‘Ripa’, it means the bank of a river, pond or lake of the surrounding landscape (Tabacchi *et al.*, 1990, Junk & Piedade, 1997, Goebel *et al.*, 2003). It is located next to streams, rivers, lakes, ponds, wetlands and have direct influence on aquatic and wildlife habitat. Riparian zone is described as the area between land and water (Chris *et al.*, 2008). Riparian vegetation is one of the main components of stream bank soil bioengineering. Understanding the concept of riparian vegetation is extremely important. Riparian zone is also known as gallery forests and streamside forests (Brinson, 1990). Such vegetations are highly threatened ecosystems as they are inherently rare habitats on earth surface (Hynes, 1970). The sediment transport processes occurring at a larger scale and a longer time frame, played an important role in shaping the structure and composition of the riparian area (Shine & Nakamura, 2005). The distributions of plants that are tolerant to either flooding or drought are also helpful in delimiting riparian ecosystems (Nilsson, 1983). The riparian zone has complex interactions among hydrology, geomorphology, light and temperature which influence the structure, dynamics and composition of riparian ecosystems (Brinson, 1990; Malanson, 1993). Riparian plants were given an important role in the river continuum concept (Vannote *et al.*, 1980; Minshall *et al.*, 1985) which predicts that the load and quality of organic matter and the biota in the stream/river channel from the head waters to the lower river courses increases with riparian vegetation and river width. The riparian ecosystems support a prevalence of vegetation typically adapted for life in saturated soil conditions (Gosselink *et al.*, 1981). The general structure of riparian vegetation consists of three layered organization of canopy trees, middle stratum of shrubs and woody climbers and herbaceous ground flora. Trees are considered as the most significant component in the riparian ecosystems (Minore and Weatherly, 1994; Pettit and Friend, 2001). Shrubs provide shade and stream bank stabilization, prevent the regeneration of trees in some riparian environments, thereby resulting in gradual succession to a shrub community (Hibbs, 1987). However in the tropical riparian flood plains, seasonal herbaceous annual vegetation dominates, where large flood disturbance prevents the recruitment of woody species. Anthropogenic activities like overgrazing, deforestation, shifting cultivation, sand mining, urbanization, dam and road constructions were found to be the major causes of deterioration of biodiversity in riparian area. Many forests are under great anthropogenic biodiversity, productivity and sustainability of the forests can be maintained (Kumar *et al.*, 2002). The floristic diversity studies have been conducted different parts of the world (Whittaker and Niering, 1965; Risser and Rice, 1971; Gentry, 1988; Linder *et al.*, 1997; Chittibabu and Parthasarathy, 2000; Sagar *et al.*, 2003; Padalia *et al.*, 2004; Appolinario *et al.*, 2005). Floristic wealth in homestead agroforestry system of Kanyakumari District was analysed (Paul and Jeeva, 2013), wetland plants of the district (Sukumaran and Jeeva, 2011; 2012) and various floristic studies were reported already from this district (Sukumaran and Parthipan, 2014; Parthipan *et al.*, 2016; Kingston *et al.*, 2006; Jose *et al.*, 2014; Arul *et al.*, 2013; Suba *et al.*, 2014; Brintha *et al.*, 2015; Geetha *et al.*, 2015). Studies on the riparian vegetation and floristic diversity of Kanyakumari district are lacking. The present

study aims at surveying the vegetation analysis on floristic biodiversity of the Kuzhithurai Thamirabarani River, which is also called as Kuzhithurai of Kanyakumari district to enlist the following plant species. This investigation gains importance because the study area faces a lot of threats, mostly anthropogenic, sand mining, flood, agricultural activities, collection of medicinal plants, collection of timber and non-timber forest products, etc., Focussing these facts the present study was attempted to enumerate the riparian angiosperms plants of the river thaminaparani in Kanyakumari district.

Material and Methods:

Study Area:

Kanyakumari district is the southernmost part of Tamil Nadu. The district lies between 77° 15' and 77° 36' of the eastern longitudes and 8° 03' and 8° 35' of the Northern Latitudes. The District is bound by Tirunelveli District on the North and the east (Fig:1). The South Eastern boundary is the Gulf of Mannar. On the South and the South West, the boundaries are the Indian Ocean and the Arabian Sea. On the West and North West it is bound by Kerala.

People and Socioculture:

A total of ca.11,37,181 people inhabit Kanyakumari district, Tamil and Malayalam are the main languages. Christians and Hindus form a sizeable percentage of the population of the district and there are a number of Muslim dominated belts in the district. The cast system in the society has weakened to a great extent especially after independence because of growth of education and improvements in transports and communication. 'Nadar' is the major community of this district. Some of the other communities of the district are *Nanjil Nadu Vellalars, Paravas, Mukthavas, Vilakki Thalanayar, Asari, Chackarevars* and *Kerala Mudalis* etc. The soil of the district is broadly classified into two major groups namely, red and alluvium soils. Red soil is further classified into red loam and sandy soils. Alluvium soil is divided into coastal and river alluvium soils. An area of the district occupied by red soil is greater than alluvial soil. The black colour of forest soil is mainly due to high contents of humus and minerals. The District has a favorable agro-climatic condition, which is suitable for growing a number of crops. The proximity of equator, its topography and other climate factors favour the growth of various crops. The paddy varieties grown in the second crop season in Thovalai and Agasteeswaram taluks are grown during the first crop season in Kalkulam and Vilavancode taluks. This shows that there is distinct variation in the climatic conditions prevailing within the district. Unlike other district in Tamil Nadu, it has a rainfall both during the South West and the North East monsoons. The South West monsoon period starts from the month of June and ends in September, while the North East monsoon period starts from October and ends in the middle of December.

River System:

The major river in the district is Thamirabarani locally known as Kuzhithurai. The origin of Tambaraparani River is in the Western Ghats latitude 8.512440 N, Longitude 77.38495 E and the river confluences with Arabian Sea near Thengapattanam, Latitude 8.242156 N, Longitude 77.16720 E. This river has two major tributaries, Kodayar and Paraliyar, with the Pechiparai dam and Perunchani dam, respectively, built across them. There are many tributaries for the Kodayar River of which Chittar I and Chittar II, with their dams, are the major ones (Fig: 2).

Figure 1: Map Showing the study area

Source : Google Map

Figure 2: Thamiraparani river and its tributaries

This river flows in two taluks respectively namely Vilavancode and Kalkulam viz., Kodayar, Pechiparai, Kadayalumoodu, Kaliyal, Thirparappu, Thiruvattar, Kuzhithurai, ST Mancadu, Kanapathiyankadavu and Thenkappattanam about 56 kilometres west of Kanyakumari district.

Floristic Survey:

Thamiraparani River was taken up for the study of floristic diversity. Fortnightly pedestrian surveys were conducted from 2010-2013. Collection trips were organized during all season covering the entire study area of Thamiraparani River. Trails and trail-less portions of the study area were walked along the two sides of the river. Extensive collection of plants was made in the study area. At the time of collection, similar species were difficult to identify in the field, so as a precautions vouchers were collected as replicates. Collection of information such as family and binomial name, habit, the habitat of the field voucher, plant and those characteristics which cannot be observed from the pressed specimens were recorded.

Enumeration of the Species:

The plants which can be identified (flowering plants) in the field were recorded and all other specimens were critically observed; flowers of unidentified plants were preserved and dissected. They were checked with the help of regional flora(Gamble and Fischer (1915 - 1936), Nair and Henry (1983,1987,1989), Matthew(1982, 1999), Mohanan and Henry (1994), Nayar *et al.*,(2014)). Rare, Endemic and Threatened (RET) species were identified with the help of Nayar and Sastry (1987, 1988, 1990),Nayar (1996). Identification was further confirmed after matching the specimens with authentic or type sheets in Centre for Biodiversity and Biotechnology (CBB), St.Xavier’s College, Palayamkottai, Tropical Botanical Garden and Research Institute (TBGRI), Palode and Calicut University Herbarium Kerala. The enumerated plants were listed as botanical name, followed by vernacular names, family, habit, conservation status. The preserved specimens were deposited in the Department of Botany, Nesamony Memorial Christian Collge, Marthandam.

Results:

Taxonomically, a total of 720 species belonging to 449 genera under 126 families were recorded from the study area. Out of the 720 taxa ,dicots were represented by 551 (76.5%) species under 348 genera belonging to 101 families, and monocots 169 (23.5%) species belonging to 101 genera under 25 families (Figure: 3). Life form of floristic diversity of the study area showed that herbaceous species exhibited maximum. The constituting by 219 herbs (30.4%), followed by trees 192 (26.7%), 113 (15.7%) shrubs, 50 (6.9%) climbing shrubs, 37 (5.2%) perennial herbs, 24 (3.3%) annual herbs, 15 (2 %) twining herbs, 12 (1.7%) twining shrubs, 11 (1.6%) aquatic herbs, 9 (1.3%) climbing herbs, 6 (0.6%) rhizomatous herbs, 5 (0.7%) marshy herbs, 5 (0.7%) tunerous herbs, 4 (0.6%) lianas, 4 (0.4%) tuberous climbing herbs, 3 (0.4%) stragglinbg shrubs, 2 (0.3%) climbers, 2 (0.3%) climbing palms, 2 (0.3%) prostrate herbs, climbing shrub, creeping herb, epiphytic herb, parasitic shrub and parasitic twining herb were 1(0.1%) species each (Figure: 4). Poaceae was dominant family with 62 species under 41 genera followed by Fabaceae were 49 species under 34 genera and Euphorbiaceae were 31

Figure 3: Distribution of families ,genus and species enumerated in the study area

Figure 6: Economic utilities of the recorded plant species

Abbreviations:

Me: Medicinal; Fd: Food; Dye: Dye; Fr: Fodder, Oi: Oil; Po: Poison; Or: Ornamental; Fi: Fibre; Ta: Tannin; Gu: Gum; Gm: Green Manure; Ti: Timber; Pp: Paper pulp; Re: Resin; Sw: Soft wood; Pe: Perfume, Bm: Basket making; Be: Beverage; Mm: Mat making; La: Latex; Th: Thatching; Sb: Soil binder, Fp: Fish poison; Sh: Shampoo; To: Toddy; Fen: Fencing; In: Ink; De: Detergent.

Figure 7: Conservation status of recorded plant species in the study area

Abbreviations: C: Common; E: Endemic; Ex: Exotic; R: Rare; V: Vulnerable.

species under 13 genera as on family ranking analysis (Figure: 5) and their, rare and threatened based on Red data book, out of 720 taxa collected from the study area, 114 species were recorded.

Some of the plant species are *Aegle marbelos*, *Ampelocissus indica*, *Andrographis paniculata*, *Arenga wightii*, *Aristolochia indica*, *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, *Burea monnosperma*, *Calamus rotang*, *Caralluma adscendens*, *Ceropegia candelabrum*, *Commelina clavata*, *Diospyros malabarica*, *Drosera burmannii*, *Ficus beddomei*, *Hemidesmus indicus*, *Holigarana aronottiana*, *H.grahamii*, *Hopea parviflora*, *Hydnocarpus alpina*, *H.pentandrus*, *Leea indica*, *Mallotus tetracoccus*, *Memecylon duck*, *Myxopyrum smilacifolium*, *Naregamia alata*, *Nothopegia colebrookiana*, *Ophiorrhiza mungos*, *Persea macrantha*, *Rauwolfia serpentina*, *Santalum album*, *Saraca asoca*, *Semecarpus travancorian*, *Strobilanthes ciliates*, *Tabarnaemontana divaricata*, *Vateria indica*. In the present observation indicates that the local people of the study area used the medicinal plants from the riparian area for treating mild ailments. Seeds, fruit, barck, tuber, leaf, rhizome and whole plants were used for medicinal purposes. Besides the riparian flora play a crucial role in development of socioeconomic value of the vicinity in thampiraparani river. However the plant species also provide food, fodder, dye, oil, poison, fibre, tannin, gum, green manure, timber, paper pulp, resin, softwood, perfume, basket making, beverage, mat making, latex, thatching, soil binder, fish poison, shampoo, toddy, fencing, ink, detergent (Figure: 6). The conservation status of the recorded plant species were; 568 common (70.6%), 98 exotic (13.6%) and 114 (15.8%) species are Rare, Endemic and Threatened (RET) categories (Figure:7).

Discussion and Conclusion:

The present study revealed that the riparian zones of Thampiraparani river of Kanyakumari district had a rich floristic wealth. Riparian vegetation represents a mesic plant community type that is adapted to and requires a supplemental source of water, either fluvial or from lateral subsurface flow converging within the valley bottom. Consequently, the models in this study predicted riparian vegetation to occur on low gradient sites, at

low vertical elevations above the stream channel, in areas of higher topographic wetness indices (indicating a wetter site), and in wider valleys. Floral composition of angiosperms were high in Bharathappuzha (Cherullipadi and Paul, 2016). Poaceae was dominant family which predominantly contain annual plants able to survive in diverse ecological conditions in Mahi river (Amita et al., 2015), herbaceous plants were occupied their dominancy than trees and shrubs in Mini river (Shah et al., 2015). The present study has been concentrated only on angiosperms as it is a major group of the plant kingdom. In annual rivers, Asteraceae was dominant biggest family followed by Fabaceae, Myrtaceae, Cyperaceae, Rubiaceae and Poaceae was less in the riparian forest of Southwestern Brazil (Faxina et al., 2015). This vegetation profile modification is due to the frequent floodplain disturbances, and wetland nature of the terrain to establish Poaceae members. Around 2,015 species of flowering plants were endemic to peninsular India (Nayar, 1996). The Western Ghats are on the brink of endemic plant collapse, about 1500 species have a highly fragmented population and at least 50 endemic species have not be relocated after repeated surveys (Nayar 1998). The Western Ghats serves as high percentage of endemic species, about 48% of 4000 species occur in this region (Gopalan & Henry 2000). In the Sacred forests of Kanyakumari district, 12 plant species were recorded as RET species (Sukumaran, 2008). 51 angiosperms were documented RET plants from Nilgiri in Madukkarai forests of southern Western Ghats (Kumar et al, 2012.). The current study in Thamiraparani river revealed 111 species listed in RET category. *Artocarpus hirsutus*, *Pandanus canaranus*, *Aegle marmelos*, *Alpinia galanga*, *Careya arborea*, *Colocassia esculenta*, *Cyperus distans*, *Derris scandens*, *Justicia gendarussa*, *Millingtonia hortensis* and *Streblus asper* were widely distributed species and their presence in different types of vegetation reflects their wide adaptability. Some species are highly sensitive to ecological perturbation and their distribution had been narrowed down. This study was to predict spatial patterns of riparian vegetation employing identity. The floristic wealth can be used to successfully predict the presence of certain individual species, as well as the presence of riparian vegetation, using either continuous plot weighted wetland threshold score designed to represent a dominance of riparian species. Giant trees acts a barrier protecting the river banks from soil erosion and the check dams slow down the flow of the river where by recharging the ground water and increasing the water table. Neighbouring agricultural activities along the riparian landscapes, uncontrolled anthropogenic activities are affecting the allied biodiversity of the riparian zones. This investigation focused on floristic composition and present status of the riparian vegetation in the middle and lower reaches of the Thamiraparani River brings out many significant features. This enables the analysis of factors relevant to river protection, biodiversity conservation and other social, economic and ecological dependence.

Table 1: Plant species recorded from the study site

Botanical name	V.N/T.N	Family	H	S
<i>Abelmoschus angulosus</i> Steud.ex.Mast.	Kattuvendai	Malvaceae	S	C
<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Kuntimani	Fabaceae	C	E
<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.)Sweet .	Thuthi	Malvaceae	S	C
<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> Benth.	Acacia	Fabaceae	T	Ex
<i>Acacia mangium</i> Willd.	Manigium	Fabaceae	T	Ex
<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (Benth.)Brenan.	Karivelam	Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Acacia pennata</i> (L.) Willd.		Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	Kuppaimeni	Euphorbiaceae	H	C
<i>Acalypha lanceolata</i> Willd.		Euphorbiaceae	H	C
<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> DC.		Asclepiadaceae	H	C
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Nayuruvi	Amaranthaceae	H	E
<i>Achyranthes bidentata</i> Blume	Rettai Nayuruvi	Amaranthaceae	H	C
<i>Acmella radicans</i> (Jacq.)R.K.Jansen		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Acorus calamus</i> L.		Araceae	H	C
<i>Actinodaphne wightiana</i> (Kuntze.)Noltie		Lauraceae	T	C
<i>Adenantha pavonina</i> L.	Manchadi	Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Adenium obesum</i> Roem. & Schult.	Adenium	Apocyanaceae	S	C
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> Nees-Pl.Asiat.Rar.(Wallich)	Adathoda	Acanthaceae	S	C
<i>Adhatoda zeylanica</i> Mediquis.		Acanthaceae	S	C
<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.)	Vilvom	Rutaceae	T	E
<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.)Juss.ex Schult.	Cherukanpoolai	Amaranthaceae	H	C
<i>Aeschynomene aspera</i> L.		Fabaceae	S	C
<i>Aganosma cymosum</i> (Roxb.)G.Don.		Apocyanaceae	C	C
<i>Agave cantula</i> Roxb.	Kattalai	Agavaceae	H	C
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	muyal Pachilai	Asteraceae	H	Ex
<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Perumaram	Simoroubaceae	T	C
<i>Alangium salvifolium</i> (L.f.)Wangerin.	Thavittai	Cornaceae	T	C
<i>Albizia chinensis</i> (Osbeck .)Merr.	Vaahai	Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (L.)Benth.	Vaagai	Mimosaceae	T	C
<i>Albizia saman</i> (Jacq.)F.Muell.	Vaahai	Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Alloteropsis cimicina</i> (L.)Stapf.	Pull	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.)Burm.f.	Chottu Kattalai	Liliaceae	H	Ex
<i>Alpinia galanga</i> (L.)Willd.	Perarathai	Zingiberaceae	H	C
<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.)W.T.Aiton.	Ezhilampalai	Apocynaceae	T	C

<i>Alstonia venanata</i> R.Br.	Paalai	Apocyanaceae	T	E
<i>Alternanthera paronychioides</i> A.St.Hil.		Amaranthaceae	H	Ex
<i>Alternanthera pungens</i> Kunth	Ottaramul	Amaranthaceae	H	Ex
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.)R.Br.ex D.C.	Ponnakanni	Amaranthaceae	H	C
<i>Amaranthes spinosus</i> L.	Mullukeerai	Amaranthaceae	H	Ex
<i>Amaranthes viridi</i> L.	Kuppaikeerai	Amaranthaceae	H	C
<i>Ampelocissus indica</i> (L.)Planch.	Kaattumunthiri	Vitaceae	C	R
<i>Ampelocissus latifolia</i> (Roxb.)Planch.	Kaattumunthiri	Vitaceae	C	C
<i>Anabaena azolla</i> Strarb.	Azolla	Azollaceae	H	C
<i>Anacardium occidentals</i> L.	Kolla Mavu	Anacardiaceae	T	Ex
<i>Anamirta cocculus</i> (L.)Wight & Arn.	Kakkakolyvithai	Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Ananas comosus</i> (L.)Merr.	Annasi	Bromeliaceae	H	Ex
<i>Andrographis alata</i> (Burm.f.)Wall.ex Nees	Kirisathu	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.)Nees.	Kiriyathu	Acanthaceae	H	E
<i>Andrographis serpyllifolia</i> (Vahl)Wight	Siryankai	Acanthaceae	H	E
<i>Anisomeles indica</i> (L.)Kuntze.	Peimiratti	Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Anisomeles malabarica</i> (L.)R.Br.	Peimiratti	Lamiaceae	S	C
<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Munthiri	Annonaceae	T	Ex
<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb.ex.DC.)Wall.ex.Guill. &Perr.		Combretaceae	T	C
<i>Antidesma acidum</i> Retz.		Euphorbiaceae	S	C
<i>Antidesma ghaesembilla</i> Gaertn.		Euphorbiaceae	S	C
<i>Antidesma montanum</i> Blume.		Phyllanthaceae	T	C
<i>Antigonon leptopus</i> Hook.& Arn.		Polygonaceae	C	Ex
<i>Aponogeton appendiculatus</i> H.Bruggen.		Aponogetonaceae	H	C
<i>Aponogeton natans</i> (L.)Engler & Krause		Aponogetonaceae	H	C
<i>Archidendron bigeminum</i> (L.) I.C.Nielsen.		Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Areca catechu</i> L.	Kamuku	Arecaceae	T	Ex
<i>Arenga wightii</i> Griff.	Aazhathenku	Arecaceae	T	E
<i>Argemone Mexicana</i> L.var.	Mexican kaduku	Papavaraceae	H	Ex
<i>Argyrea boseana</i> Santapau & V.Patel		Convolvulaceae	L	C
<i>Argyrea elliptica</i> (Roth)Choisy.		Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Argyrea sericea</i> Dalzell.		Convolvulaceae	C	E
<i>Arisaema leschenaultii</i> Blume.	Pambuchozham	Araceae	H	C
<i>Aristida setacea</i> Retz.	Moonchuttai	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Aristolochia gigasvar</i> S.watson	Iswawmooli	Aristolochiaceae	H	R
<i>Aristolochia indica</i> L.	Karudakodi	Aristolochiaceae	C	E
<i>Aristolochia tagala</i> Cham.	Karudakodi	Aristolochiaceae	C	C
<i>Artabotrys hexapetalus</i> (L.) Bhandari.	Manorenjitham	Annonaceae	C	C
<i>Artabotrys zeylanicus</i> Hook.f.& Thomson	Manorenjitham	Annonaceae	C	C
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lam.	Pala	Moraceae	T	E
<i>Artocarpus hirsutus</i> Lam.	Ayani	Moraceae	T	E
<i>Asparagus plumosus</i> (Barker)Oberm.	Sathavari	Liliaceae	C	C
<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Sathavari	Asparagaceae	C	C
<i>Asystasia gangetica</i> (L.)T.And.	Mithikeerai	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Atropa belladona</i> L.		Solanaceae	S	R
<i>Axonopus compressus</i> (SW.)P.Beauv.	Erumaipull	Poaceae	H	Ex
<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss.	Veppu	Meliaceae	T	C
<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.)Pennell	Brammi	Scrophulariaceae	H	C
<i>Balbostylis barbata</i> (Rottb.) C.B.Clarke	Korai	Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Bambusa bambos</i> (L.) Voss.	Mulai	Poaceae	T	C
<i>Bambusa tulda</i> Roxb.	Mulai	Poaceae	T	R
<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> Schrad.	Olaimulai	Poaceae	T	Ex
<i>Barleria buxifolia</i> L.	Pochimull	Acanthaceae	S	C
<i>Barleria cuspidata</i> Heyne ex Nees	Pochimull	Acanthaceae	S	E
<i>Barleria mysorensis</i> Heyne er Roth	Pochimull	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Barleria nitida</i> Nees	Miullipoondu	Acanthaceae	S	C
<i>Barleria prionitis</i> L.	Chullipoo	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Basilicum polystachion</i> Moench.	Pull	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Bauhinia malabarica</i> Lam.	Begonia	Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Bauhinia phoenicea</i> Wight & Arn.	Mantharam	Fabaceae	C	E
<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam.	Mantharam	Caesalpinjiaceae	T	C
<i>Biophytum reinwardtii</i> (Zucc.)Klotzsch	Mukkutti	Oxalidaceae	H	C
<i>Biophytum sensitivum</i> (L.)D.C.	Mukkutti	Oxalidaceae	H	C
<i>Blainvillea acmella</i> (L.) Philipson.		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i> (L.) Heyne ex Roth	Vedipachilai	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Blumea lacera</i> (Burm.f.)DC.	Kaatumullanki	Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Blumea membranacea</i> Wall.ex. DC.		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Blumea virens</i> Wall.ex . DC.		Asteraceae	S	C
<i>Boerhaavia repens</i> L.	Thazhuthami	Nyctaginaceae	H	C
<i>Bombax insigne</i> Wall.	Neruppumalar	Bombacaceae	T	C
<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Panai	Arecaceae	T	C

<i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i> Willd.	Paperpoo	Nyctaginaceae	C	Ex
<i>Brachiaria ramosa</i> (L.) Stapf.	Pull	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Brassica campestris</i> L.	Kaduku	Capparidaceae	H	C
<i>Breynia retusa</i> (Dennst.) Alston.		Euphorbiaceae	S	C
<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> (Lam.) Oken.	Chodakku	Crassulaceae	H	Ex
<i>Buchanania lanzan</i> Spreng.		Anacardiaceae	T	C
<i>Burea monnosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Chamathai	Fabaceae	T	E
<i>Burmannia pusilla</i> (Miers.) Thwaites.		Burmanniaceae	H	C
<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i> (L.) Roxb.	Kalanchi	Fabaceae	C	C
<i>Cajanus albicans</i> (Wight & Arn.) Maesen	Valli thuavrai	Fabaceae	C	C
<i>Cajanus lineatus</i> (Wight & Arn.) Maesen.	Kaatu thuvurai	Fabaceae	S	E
<i>Caladium bicolor</i> Wightii (Lem.) Engl.	Jesus heart	Araceae	H	Ex
<i>Calamus rotang</i> L.	Pirappankizhanku	Araceae	C	E
<i>Calamus travancoricus</i> Bedd. ex Becc.	Perampu	Arecaceae	C	E
<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i> L.	Punnai	Calophyllaceae	T	C
<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) R.Br. W.T. Aiton.	Erukku	Apocyanaceae	S	C
<i>Calycopteris floribunda</i> (Roxb.) Poir.	Nilatvahai	Combretaceae	S	C
<i>Camellia sinensis</i> (L.) Kuntze var.		Camelliaceae	S	Ex
<i>Canarium strictum</i> Roxb.	Karunkunthirikkam	Surseraceae	T	C
<i>Canna indica</i> L. var.	Azhakuchembu	Cannaceae	S	Ex
<i>Cansjera rheedii</i> J.F. Gmel.		Opiliaceae	C	C
<i>Canthium angustifolium</i> Roxb.	Kaarai	Rubiaceae	S	C
<i>Canthium diococcum</i> (Gaertn.) Teijsm & Binn. var. <i>diccocum</i> .	Irumparuthan	Rubiaceae	S	C
<i>Capparis sepiala</i> L.	Aathandai	Capparidaceae	C	C
<i>Capparis zeylanica</i> L.	Athandai	Capparidaceae	S	C
<i>Capsicum annum</i> L.	Milagai	Solanaceae	H	C
<i>Caralluma adscendens</i> var. <i>attenuata</i> (White) Gravelly & Mayur.		Asclepiadaceae	H	E
<i>Caralluma umbellata</i> Haw.		Asclepiadaceae	H	C
<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Uzhinjai	Sapindaceae	C	C
<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb.	Naiperai	Barringtoniaceae	T	C
<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Pappali	Caricaceae	T	Ex
<i>Carissa carandas</i> L.	Cherry	Apocyanaceae	S	C
<i>Carissa inermis</i> Vahl.	Muchu	Apocyanaceae	S	E
<i>Carissa spinarum</i> L.	Muchu ilai	Apocyanaceae	S	C
<i>Carmona retusa</i> (Vahl.) Masamune.	Poripazham	Boraginaceae	S	C
<i>Caryota urens</i> L.	Olatti	Arecaceae	T	C
<i>Cassia alata</i> L.	Vandukolli	Caesalpinaceae	S	Ex
<i>Cassia auriculata</i> L.	Avaram	Fabaceae	S	C
<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Kanikonttai	Caesalpinaceae	T	C
<i>Cassia hirsuta</i> L.	Cherukontai	Caesalpinaceae	S	Ex
<i>Cassia mimosoides</i> L.	Appattumullu	Caesalpinaceae	H	C
<i>Cassia occidentalis</i> L.	Peithakarai	Caesalpinaceae	S	Ex
<i>Cassia pumila</i> Lam.	Mullila thottadi	Fabaceae	H	C
<i>Cassia siamea</i> Lam.	Thakarai	Caesalpinaceae	T	C
<i>Cassia tora</i> L.	Peithakarai	Caesalpinaceae	H	C
<i>Casuarina litorea</i> L.	Kattadi	Casurinaceae	T	Ex
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i> L.	Attanari	Apocyanaceae	H	Ex
<i>Cayratia japonica</i> (Thunb.) Gagnep.	Vishaperandai	Menispermaceae	S	C
<i>Cayratia pedata</i> (Lam.) Gagnep.	Kattuperanda	Menispermaceae	C	R
<i>Cayratia trifolia</i> (L.) Domin	Kaaturperandai	Menispermaceae	H	C
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Ilavu	Bombacaceae	T	Ex
<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i> Willd.		Celastraceae	C	C
<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	African Kozhipoo	Amaranthaceae	H	Ex
<i>Celosia cristata</i> L.	Kozhipoo	Amaranthaceae	H	C
<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urban	Vallarai	Apiaceae	H	C
<i>Centrosema pubescens</i> Benth.	Kattu sanku pushpam	Fabaceae	C	Ex
<i>Ceropegia candelabrum</i> L.	Koppalipoo	Asclepiadaceae	C	E
<i>Chassalia ophiosyloides</i> (Wallich) Craiv		Rubiaceae	S	C
<i>Chloris barbata</i> SW.	Poonaipull	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (L.) King & Robinson	Poochedi	Asteraceae	H	Ex
<i>Chrysophyllum roxburghii</i> G. Don.	Irukolli	Sapotaceae	T	C
<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i> (Retz.) Trin.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> (L.) J. Presl	Suganthamaram	Lauraceae	T	Ex
<i>Cinnamomum macrocarpum</i> Hook. f.	Pattai	Lauraceae	T	E
<i>Cinnamomum malabatum</i> (Burm. f.) J. Presl.	Pattai	Lauraceae	T	E
<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J. Presl.	Pattai	Lauraceae	T	C
<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Kaatumunthiri	Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L.	Perandai	Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Cissus vitignea</i> L.	Kaatu Thiratchai	Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Citrus aurantium</i> L.	Narangai	Rutaceae	T	Ex

<i>Citrus medica</i> L.var.liman L.	Kommatimathulai	Rutaceae	T	C
<i>Clematis gouriana</i> Roxb.ex.DC.	Nikidakodi	Ranunculaceae	C	C
<i>Cleome aspera</i> Koen.ex.DC.	Peikaduku	Capparidaceae	H	C
<i>Cleome ruidosperma</i> DC.	Poikaduku	Capparidaceae	H	C
<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Naaikaduku	Capparidaceae	H	C
<i>Clerodendrum indicum</i> (L.)Kuntze	Peruvilai	Lamiaceae	S	C
<i>Clerodendrum infortunatum</i> L.	Peruvilai	Verbenaceae	S	C
<i>Clerodendrum paniculatum</i> L.	Arasampoo	Verbenaceae	S	Ex
<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.	Sankupushpam	Fabaceae	C	Ex
<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voilgt.	Kovakkai	Cucurbitaceae	C	C
<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i> L.	Kattukodi	Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.	Thennai	Arecaceae	T	C
<i>Coffea arabica</i> L.	Kaappi	Rubiaceae	S	Ex
<i>Coldenia procumbens</i> L.		Boraginaceae	H	C
<i>Colocasia esculenta</i> (L.)Schott	Chembu	Araceae	H	C
<i>Combretum albidum</i> G.Don.		Combretaceae	C	C
<i>Commelina attenuata</i> Koen.ex.Vhal.	Vazha pachilai	Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Vazha pachilai	Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Commelina clavata</i> C.B.Clarke.	Vazha pachilai	Commelinaceae	H	E
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm.f.	Kanankozha	Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Commelina erecta</i> L.	Vazha pachilai	Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Commelina longifolia</i> Lam.		Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Commelina Maculata</i> Edgew.		Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Commelina wightii</i> Raiz.		Commelinaceae	H	E
<i>Cordia gharaf</i> (Forssk.)Ehrenb.ex.Asch.		Boraginaceae	T	C
<i>Corypha umbraculifera</i> L.	Kodappanai	Arecaceae	T	C
<i>Costus pictus</i> D.Don.	Costus	Costaceae	H	Ex
<i>Crassocephalum crepidioids</i> (Benth.)S.Moore.		Asteraceae	H	Ex
<i>Crataeva nurvala</i> Vuch.Ham.	Marvilangam	Capparidaceae	T	C
<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.	Kaatu ulli	Amaryllidaceae	H	C
<i>Crinum biflorum</i> Rottb.	Kaatu venkayam	Amaryllidaceae	H	R
<i>Crossandra infundibuliformis</i> (L.) Nees in Wall.	Kanakamparam	Acanthaceae	S	C
<i>Crotalaria heyneana</i> (Wight & Arn.)	Killupaichedi	Fabaceae	S	E
<i>Crotalaria pallida</i> Dryand.		Fabaceae	H	C
<i>Crotalaria retusa</i> L.	Kilukilupan	Fabaceae	H	C
<i>Crotalaria verrucosa</i> L.		Fabaceae	H	C
<i>Croton bonplandianus</i> Baill.	Mannennaichedi	Euphorbiaceae	H	Ex
<i>Croton malabaricus</i> Bedd.	Thavittu plavu	Euphorbiaceae	T	E
<i>Cryptocoryne retrospirals</i> (Roxb.)Kunth		Araceae	H	C
<i>Cucumis sativus</i> L.	Vellari	Cucurbitaceae	C	C
<i>Curculigo orchioides</i> Gaertn.	Nillapanai	Hypoxidaceae	H	C
<i>Curcuma amada</i> Roxb.	Mankai inchi	Zingiberaceae	H	C
<i>Curcuma aromatica</i> Salisb.	Kasthurimanjal	Zingiberaceae	H	C
<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Manjal	Zingiberaceae	H	C
<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb.	Moodillathali	Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Cyamopsis tetragonoloba</i> (L.)Taub.		Fabaceae	H	C
<i>Cyanotis axillaris</i> (L.)D.Don. Ex Sweet.	Neerpulli	Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Cyanotis cristata</i> (L.)D.Don.	Kuthiraiikulampadi	Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Cyanotis cucullata</i> Kunth.		Commelinaceae	H	E
<i>Cyanotis tuberosa</i> (Roxb.)Schultes. & Schultes.f.	Valukai kizhanku	Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Cyanotis villosa</i> (Spreng.)Schultes.f.		Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Cyathea gigantea</i> (Wall.ex.Hook.) Holttum		Cyatheaceae	S	R
<i>Cyathula prostrata</i> (L.)Blume.		Amaranthaceae	H	C
<i>Cyclea peltata</i> (Lam.)Hook.f. & Thomson	Thazhi	Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Cymbidium aloifolium</i> (L.)Sw.	Cymbidium	Orchidaceae	H	R
<i>Cymbogon martinii</i> (Roxb.)W.Watson.	Elumichai pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Cymbopogon flexuosus</i> (Steud.)P.Watson.	Chukkunari	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Cynanchum callialatum</i> Buch.Ham.ex Wight		Asclepiadaceae	C	C
<i>Cynanchum tunicatum</i> (Rtez.)Alston		Asclepiadaceae	C	C
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.)Pers.	Arukampullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Cyperus compressus</i> L.	Korai	Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Cyperus diffusus</i> Vahl var.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Cyperus distans</i> L.f.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Cyperus haspan</i> L.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Cyperus nutons</i> Vahl.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Muthankai	Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Cyrtococcum trigonum</i> (Retz.)A.Camus		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Willd.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Oomathai	Solanaceae	S	C
<i>Datura stramonium</i> L.var.innervis(Juss.)		Solanaceae	S	Ex
<i>Debregeasia longifolia</i> (Burm.f.)Wedd.		Urticaceae	T	C

<i>Decalepis arayalpathra</i> Joseph & Chandrasekaran		Apocynaceae	S	E
<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> (Roxb.)Nees.	Mulai	Poaceae	T	C
<i>Dentrophthoe falcata</i> (L.f.)Ettingsh.	Itthi	Loranthaceae	S	E
<i>Derris benthamii</i> (Thwaites.)	Derris	Fabaceae	C	C
<i>Derris scandens</i> (Roxb.)Benth.	Derris	Fabaceae	C	C
<i>Derris trifoliata</i> (Lour.)	Derris	Fabaceae	C	C
<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L.)DC.	Orilai	Fabaceae	S	C
<i>Desmodium heterophyllum</i> (Willd.)DC.		Fabaceae	H	C
<i>Desmodium motorium</i> (Houtt.) Nerr.	Thozhukanni	Fabaceae	S	C
<i>Desmodium triflorum</i> (L.)D.C.	Kasukosi	Fabaceae	H	C
<i>Dictyospermum montanum</i> Wight.		Commelinaceae	H	C
<i>Digitaria longiflora</i> (Retz.)Pers	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Digitaria marginata</i> Link	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Dillenia pentagyna</i> Roxb.	Nai thekku	Dilleniaceae	T	C
<i>Dioscorea alata</i> L.	Kaichil	Dioscoreaceae	C	C
<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L.	Kaichil kizhanku	Dioscoreaceae	C	C
<i>Dioscorea oppositifolia</i> L.	Valli kaichil	Dioscoreaceae	C	C
<i>Dioscorea pentaphylla</i> L.	Kaichil Valli	Dioscoreaceae	C	C
<i>Diospyros buxifolia</i> (Blume.)Hiern		Ebenaceae	T	C
<i>Diospyros malabarica</i> (Desr.)Kostel.	Panachai	Ebenaceae	T	E
<i>Diospyros paniculata</i> Dalzell.	Karimaram	Ebenaceae	T	C
<i>Dipteracanthus prostratus</i> (Poir.)Nees.		Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Dolichandrone atrovirens</i> (Heyne.ex.Roth.)Sprague.		Bignoniaceae	T	E
<i>Dolichandrone falcata</i> (Wall.ex.DC.)Seem.		Bignoniaceae	T	R
<i>Drosera burmannii</i> DC.	Drosera	Droseraceae	H	E
<i>Drymaria cordata</i> (L.)Willd.ex Roem. & Schult.subsp.diandra (Blume)Duke.		Caryophyllaceae	H	C
<i>Dyschoriste madurensis</i> (Burn.f.) Kuntze		Acanthaceae	S	C
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.)	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Eclipta alba</i> (L.) Hassk.	Karisalankanni	Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> Var. dixitii.	Karisalankanni	Asteraceae	H	E
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.)	Akayathamarai	Pontederiaceae	H	Ex
<i>Elaeocarpus serratus</i> L.	Karai	Elaeocarpaceae	T	C
<i>Elaeocarpus tuberculatus</i> Roxb.	Ruthiratchai	Elaeocarpaceae	T	C
<i>Elatostema acuminatum</i> (Poir.)Brongn.		Urticaceae	H	C
<i>Elephantopus scaber</i> L.	Anachavittadi	Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> (L.)Maton		Zingiberaceae	H	C
<i>Eluesine indica</i> (L.) Gaertner	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i> (L.)DC.	Muyalcheviyan chedi	Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Emilia zeylanica</i> Clarke.		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Entada rheedei</i> (Spreng.)		Fabaceae	C	C
<i>Eragrostis riparia</i> (Willd.)Nees	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Eragrostis unioloides</i> (Retz.)Nees ex Steud	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Eragrostis viscosa</i> (Retz.)Trin.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Ergos hertacce</i>	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Eriocaulon eurypeplon</i> Kom.		Eriocaulaceae	H	R
<i>Eriochloa procera</i> (Retz.) C.E.Hubb.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Erythrina variegata</i> L.	Nanthiarvattai	Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Erythralum scandens</i> Blume.		Olacaceae	C	C
<i>Euonymus indicus</i> Heyne.ex.Roxb.		Celastraceae	T	E
<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> L.	Kalli	Euphorbiaceae	T	C
<i>Euphorbia cyathophora</i> Murr.	Paaluri pullu	Euphorbiaceae	H	Ex
<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i> Desf.	Paaluri pullu	Euphorbiaceae	H	Ex
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.		Euphorbiaceae	H	C
<i>Euphorbia nivulia</i> Buch.-Ham.		Euphorbiaceae	S	C
<i>Euphorbia thymifolia</i> L.	Palkalli	Euphorbiaceae	H	C
<i>Euphorbia tirucalli</i> L.	Thirukalli	Euphorbiaceae	T	Ex
<i>Evolvulus nummularus</i> (L.)L.	Eli-kathu	Convolvulaceae	H	Ex
<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> var. argenteus.R.Br.	Vishnukiranthi	Convolvulaceae	H	C
<i>Ferula asafoetida</i> H.Karst.	Kayam	Apiaceae	H	C
<i>Ficus arnottiana</i> (Miq.)Miq.		Moraceae	T	C
<i>Ficus beddomei</i> King.		Moraceae	T	E
<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Aalamaram	Moraceae	T	C
<i>Ficus drupacea</i> Thunb.		Moraceae	T	C
<i>Ficus glomerata</i> Roxb.		Moraceae	T	C
<i>Ficus heterophylla</i> L.f.		Moraceae	S	C
<i>Ficus hispida</i> L.f.	Kattathi	Moraceae	T	C
<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Atthi	Moraceae	T	C
<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Arasamaram	Moraceae	T	C
<i>Fimbristylis aestivalis</i> (Retz.)Vahl.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Fimbristylis argentea</i> (Rottb.)Vahl.		Cyperaceae	H	C

<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> (L.)Vahl.ssp.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Fimbristylis tenera</i> Rome.& Schult.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Fimbristylis ovata</i> (Burm.f.) Kern		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Burm.f.)Merr.		Flacoutiaceae	C	C
<i>Flueggea leucopyrus</i> Willd.	Benpoolathi	Phyllanthaceae	S	C
<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> L.	Mangustan	Clusiaceae	T	Ex
<i>Gardenia angusta</i> (L.) Merr.		Rubiaceae	S	Ex
<i>Gliricidia sepium</i> (Jacq.)Walp.	Cheemakontai	Fabaceae	T	Ex
<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	Kalappaikizhanku	Colchicaceae	C	C
<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> Torr.		Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Gomphrena globosa</i> L.	Vadamalli	Amaranthaceae	H	Ex
<i>Gomphrena serrata</i> L.	Pei-vadamalli	Amaranthaceae	H	Ex
<i>Goniothalamus cardiopetalus</i> Dalzell-Hookers J.Bot.		Annonaceae	T	E
<i>Gossypium arboreum</i> L.		Malvaceae	S	R
<i>Grewia bracteata</i> B.Heyne ex Benth.		Tiliaceae	T	C
<i>Grewia emarginata</i> Buch.Ham.ex DC.		Tiliaceae	T	C
<i>Grewia tilifolia</i> Vahl.		Tiliaceae	T	C
<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i> (Retz.)Schult.	Chakkarai kolli	Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Gynura nitida</i> DC.		Asteraceae	H	E
<i>Hedyotis albo-nervia</i> Bedd.	Pattsuchedi	Rubiaceae	S	E
<i>Hedyotis Brevicealyx</i> Sivarajan,Biju&B. Mathew	Pattsuchedi	Rubiaceae	H	C
<i>Hedyotis corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam.	Pattsuchedi	Rubiaceae	H	C
<i>Hedyotis herbace</i> (L.)Roxb.	Pattsuchedi	Rubiaceae	H	C
<i>Hedyotis membranacea</i> Thwaites.		Rubiaceae	S	R
<i>Hedyotis trinervia</i> (Retz.) Roemer&Schultes	Pattsuchedi	Rubiaceae	H	C
<i>Helianthus annus</i> L.	Chooriyakanthi	Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Valampiri Idampiri	Malvaceae	S	C
<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L.		Boraginaceae	H	C
<i>Heliotropium marifolium</i> Retz.		Boraginaceae	H	C
<i>Heliotropium supinum</i> L.		Boraginaceae	H	C
<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.)R.Br.ex Schult.	Nannari	Apocynaceae	C	E
<i>Heteropogon controtus</i> (L.)P.Beav.ex.Roem. & Schultes.		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Hibiscus cannabinus</i> L.	Uppinichi	Malvaceae	H	C
<i>Hibiscus hispidissimus</i> Griff.	Uppinichi	Malvaceae	C	C
<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L.	Chembaruthi	Malvaceae	S	Ex
<i>Hibiscus tiliaceus</i> L.		Malvaceae	T	C
<i>Holigarana aronottiana</i> Hook.f.	Charu	Anacardiaceae	T	E
<i>Holigarana grahamii</i> (Wight.)Kurz.	Charu	Anacardiaceae	T	R
<i>Hopea parviflora</i> Bedd.		Dipterocarpaceae	T	E
<i>Hopea ponga</i> (Dennst.)Mabb.		Dipterocarpaceae	T	E
<i>Hugonia mystax</i> L.	Hoogonia	Linaceae	S	C
<i>Humboldtia vahliana</i> Wight.		Fabaceae	T	E
<i>Hybanthes enneaspermus</i> (L.)F.Muell.	Orilai thamarai	Violaceae	H	C
<i>Hydnocarpus alpina</i> Wt.		Achariaceae	T	E
<i>Hydnocarpus pentandrus</i> (Buch.-Ham.)Oken.		Achariaceae	T	E
<i>Hydrilla verticillata</i> C.Presl	Hydrilla	Hydrocharitaceae	H	C
<i>Hygrophila balsamica</i> (L.f.)Rafin.	Neermulli	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Hygrophila ringens</i> (L.)Steud.	Neermulli	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Hygrophila schulli</i> (Buch.-Ham.)		Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Hymenachne acutigluma</i> (Steud.)		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Hyptis capitata</i> Jacq.		Lamiaceae	H	Ex
<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i> (L.)Poi.	Narichappai	Lamiaceae	H	Ex
<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i> (L.)R.Br. W.T.Ation.		Apocyanaceae	C	C
<i>Impatiens acaulis</i> .Arn.		Balsaminaceae	H	C
<i>Impatiens verticillata</i> Wight.		Balsaminaceae	H	E
<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> L.	Nilamari	Fabaceae	S	C
<i>Indoneesiella echioides</i> (L.) Sreem.		Fabaceae	H	C
<i>Indoneesiella eshioides</i> (L.) Sreem	Kirisathu	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Ipomea alba</i> L.		Convolvulaceae	C	Ex
<i>Ipomea aquatica</i> Forsskal.	Kacheripoo	Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Ipomea batatas</i> (L.)Poir.		Convolvulaceae	C	Ex
<i>Ipomea cairica</i> (L.)		Convolvulaceae	C	Ex
<i>Ipomea carnia</i> Jacq.ssp.fistulosa(Mart.ex.Choisy)D.f.Austin.		Convolvulaceae	S	Ex
<i>Ipomea mauritiana</i> Jacq.		Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Ipomea obscura</i> (L.)Ker Gawl.		Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Ipomea pes-caprae</i> (L.)R.Br.		Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Ipomea pes-tigridis</i> (L.)		Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Ipomea violacea</i> (L.)		Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Isachne fischeri</i> Bor.		Poaceae	H	E
<i>Isachne miliacea</i> Roth.		Poaceae	H	C

<i>Ixora brachiata</i> Roxb.	Thetti	Rubiaceae	T	E
<i>Ixora coccinea</i> L.	Thetti	Rubiaceae	S	C
<i>Ixora johnsonii</i> Hook.f.	Thetti	Rubiaceae	S	E
<i>Ixora nigricans</i> R.Br.ex Wight & Arn.		Rubiaceae	S	C
<i>Jasminum angustifolia</i> (L.)Willd.	Pichi	Oleaceae	C	R
<i>Jasminum azoricum</i> L.		Oleaceae	C	C
<i>Jasminum malabaricum</i> Wight.	Mullai	Oleaceae	C	E
<i>Jasminum multiflorum</i> (Burm.f.)Andrews	Mullai	Oleaceae	C	C
<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Kattamankku	Euphorbiaceae	S	Ex
<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Kattamanakku	Euphorbiaceae	S	Ex
<i>Justicia diffusa</i> Willd.		Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Justicia gendarussa</i> Burm.f.		Acanthaceae	S	C
<i>Justicia glauca</i> Rott.		Acanthaceae	H	E
<i>Justicia nagpurensis</i> V.A.W.Graham.		Acanthaceae	H	E
<i>Justicia prostrata</i> (Roxb.ex.Clarke)Gamb.		Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Justicia trinervia</i> Vahl.		Acanthaceae	H	E
<i>Kleinia grandiflora</i> (Will.ex. DC.)N.Rani.		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Knoxia sumatrensis</i> var. <i>linearis</i> (Gamble.)R.Bhattacharjee & Deb		Rubiaceae	H	E
<i>Kyllinga brevifolia</i> Rottb.var. <i>brevifolia</i> .	Vellai koram	Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Kyllinga nemoralis</i> (J.R.Forst.&G.Forst.)Dandy ex Hutch. & Dalziel.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Lagenandra meeboldii</i> (Engl.)C.E.C.Fisch.		Araceae	H	E
<i>Lagenandra ovata</i> (Engl.)C.E.C.Fisch.		Araceae	H	C
<i>Lagenandra toxicaria</i> Dalzell.		Araceae	H	C
<i>Lagerstroemia speciosa</i> (L.)Pers.		Lythraceae	T	C
<i>Laggera alata</i> (D.Don.)Oliv.		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Lansea coromandelica</i> (Houtt.)Merr.	Uthi	Anacardiaceae	T	C
<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Poochedi	Verbanaceae	S	Ex
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i> L.	Maruthani	Lythraceae	S	C
<i>Leea guineense</i> G.Don.	Lee maram	Vitaceae	S	C
<i>Leea indica</i> (Burm.f.)Merr.		Vitaceae	S	E
<i>Leerisia hexandra</i> Sw.		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees.		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.)Link.	Thumpai	Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Leucas biflora</i> (Vahl.)R.Br.	Vellai thumpai	Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Leucas zeylanica</i> (L.)W.T.Aiton.		Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Limnophila indica</i> (L.)Druce		Plantaginaceae	H	C
<i>Limonia acidissima</i> L.		Rutaceae	T	C
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.)Alston.		Linderniaceae	H	C
<i>Lindernia ciliata</i> (Colsm.)Pennell.		Scrophulariaceae	H	C
<i>Lindernia crustaceae</i> (L.)F.-Muell.		Scrophulariaceae	H	C
<i>Ludwigia adscendens</i> (L.)H.Hara		Onagraceae	H	C
<i>Luffa acutangula</i> (L.)Roxb.		Cucurbitaceae	C	C
<i>Madhuca indica</i> J.f.Gmel.	Iluppai	Sapotaceae	T	C
<i>Madhuca neriifolia</i> (Moon.)H.J.Lam.	Kattu iluppai	Sapotaceae	T	C
<i>Malavastrum coromandelianum</i> (L.)Garcke.		Malvaceae	H	Ex
<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.)Mull.Arg.	Chenthura maram	Euphorbiaceae	T	C
<i>Mallotus tetracoccus</i> (Roxb.)Kurz.		Euphorbiaceae	T	C
<i>Malva sylvestris</i> L.		Malvaceae	H	C
<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Mamaram	Anacardiaceae	T	C
<i>Manihot esculenta</i> Crantz.	Maravalli	Euphorbiaceae	S	Ex
<i>Mariscus dubius</i> (Rottb.) Kük. ex G.E.C.Fischer		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Mariscus javanicus</i> (Houtt.) Merr. & F.P		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Maytenus emarginata</i> (Willd.)Ding Hou.C		Celastraceae	S	C
<i>Melanocentris jacquemontii</i> Jaub. & Spach.		Poaceae	H	R
<i>Melastoma malabathricum</i> L.	Melastoma	Melastomaceae	S	R
<i>Melochia corchorifolia</i> L.		Sterculiaceae	H	C
<i>Memecylon duck</i> Retz.		Melastomaceae	T	R
<i>Memecylon angustifolium</i> Wight.		Melastomaceae	S	C
<i>Memecylon umbellatum</i> Burm.f.		Melastomaceae	S	C
<i>Memecylon talbotianum</i> Brandis		Melastomaceae	T	E
<i>Merremia emarginata</i> (Burm.)Hallier.f.		Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Merremia hederacea</i> (Burm.f.)Hallier f.		Convolvulaceae	C	C
<i>Merremia tridentata</i> (L.) Hallier f.		Convolvulaceae	H	C
<i>Merremia vitifolia</i> (Burm.f.)Hallier.f.		Convolvulaceae	H	C
<i>Mesua ferrea</i> L.	Nangu	Calophyllaceae	T	C
<i>Michelia champaca</i> L.	Chempagam	Magnoliaceae	T	C
<i>Millettia rubiginosa</i> Wight and Arn.		Fabaceae	C	E
<i>Millingtonia hortensis</i> L.f.	Panner maram	Bignoniaceae	T	Ex
<i>Mimosa diplotricha</i> C.Wright ex. Sauvalle.		Fabaceae	S	Ex
<i>Mimosa diplotricha</i> var. <i>inermis</i> .		Mimosaceae	S	Ex

<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	Thottalvadi	Fabaceae	H	Ex
<i>Mimusops elengi</i> L.	Elengi	Sapotaceae	T	C
<i>Mollugo nudicaulis</i> Lam.	Mollugo	Aizoaceae	H	C
<i>Mollugo pentaphylla</i> L.		Aizoaceae	H	C
<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Pakarkai	Cucurbitaceae	C	C
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm.f.)C.Presl.		Pontederiaceae	H	C
<i>Morinda pubexans</i> Smith.	Manjanathi	Rubiaceae	T	C
<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Murunkai	Moringaceae	T	E
<i>Morus alba</i> L.	Mulberry	Moraceae	T	Ex
<i>Mukia maderaspatana</i> (L.)M.Roem.		Cucurbitaceae	C	C
<i>Muntiniga calabura</i> L.	Then pazham	Elaeocarpaceae	T	Ex
<i>Murraya koenigii</i> (L.) Spreng.	Karipvepillai	Rutaceae	T	C
<i>Murraya paniculata</i> (L.) Jack.		Rutaceae	S	C
<i>Musa paradisiaca</i> L.	Vazhai	Musaceae	H	C
<i>Mussaenda frondosa</i> L.	Mosssanda	Rubiaceae	S	C
<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt.	Jathi	Myrtaceae	T	Ex
<i>Myxopyrum smilacifolium</i> (Wall.) Blume.		Oleaceae	C	E
<i>Naravelia zeylanica</i> (L.) DC.		Ranunculaceae	C	C
<i>Naregamia alata</i> Wight. & Arn.	Nai elumitchai	Rutaceae	H	E
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertner	Ambel	Nymphaeaceae	H	C
<i>Neolitsea scrobiculata</i> Gamble		Lauraceae	T	E
<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	Arali	Apocyanaceae	S	C
<i>Nothopegia colebrookiana</i> (Wight.) Blume		Anacardiaceae	T	E
<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i> Burm.f		Nymphaeaceae	H	C
<i>Nymphaea pubescens</i> Willd.		Nymphaeaceae	H	C
<i>Ochlandra travancorica</i> (Bedd.) Gamble.		Poaceae	T	E
<i>Ocimum americanum</i> L.		Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	Thulasi	Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> L.	Ramatulasi	Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Ocimum muricata</i> L.		Lamiaceae	H	R
<i>Ocimum scantum</i> L.	Thulasi	Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> L.		Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Olex scandens</i> Roxb.		Olacaceae	S	R
<i>Olea dioica</i> Roxb.		Oleaceae	T	C
<i>Ophiorrhiza mungos</i> L.		Rubiaceae	H	E
<i>Oplismenus composites</i> (L.) P.Beauv.		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Oplismenus burmannii</i>		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Orthosiphon thymiflorus</i> (Roth) Sleasan	Kaatu Thulasi	Lamiaceae	H	C
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i> Griff	Arisi Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	Arisi	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Osbeckia aspera</i> (L.) Bl.		Melastomaceae	S	C
<i>Osbeckia virgata</i> D.Don.ex Wight & Arn.		Melastomaceae	S	C
<i>Pandanus fascicularis</i> Lam.	Thazham	Pandanaceae	T	C
<i>Pandanus odorifer</i> (Forssk.) Kuntze. Tectorius		Pandanaceae	T	C
<i>Pandanus thwaitesii</i> Martelli	Ramba ilai	Pandanaceae	S	C
<i>Pandanus unipapillatus</i> Dennst.	Kaithai	Pandanaceae	T	E
<i>Panicum brevifolium</i> (Link.) Kunth	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Panicum maximum</i> Jacq.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	Ex
<i>Panicum notatum</i> Retz.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Panicum paludosum</i> Roxb.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Panicum sumatrense</i> Roth ex Roemar & Schultes	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	Parthenium	Asteraceae	H	Ex
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i> (Retz.) A.Camus.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> P.J.Bergius.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Passiflora edulis</i> Sims	Bonjikai	Passifloraceae	C	Ex
<i>Passiflora foetida</i> L.	Cokkanpazham	Passifloraceae	C	Ex
<i>Pavetta hispidula</i> Wight & Arn.		Rubiaceae	S	R
<i>Pavonia odorata</i> Willd.	Peramutti	Rubiaceae	H	C
<i>Pennisetum pedicellatum</i> Trin.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Pennisetum polystachion</i> (L.) Schult.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Pentatropis capensis</i> (L.f.) Bullock.		Asclepiadaceae	C	R
<i>Peperomia pellucida</i> (L.) Kunth		Piperaceae	H	Ex
<i>Peperomia tetraphylla</i> (G.Forst.) Hook. & Arn.		Piperaceae	H	C
<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	Veliparuthi	Asclepiadaceae	S	C
<i>Peristrophe paniculata</i> (Forssk.) Brummitt.		Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Perotis indica</i> (L.) Kuntze	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Persea macrantha</i> (Nees.) Kosterm.		Lauraceae	T	E
<i>Phoenix loureirii</i> Kunth.		Arecaceae	S	R
<i>Phoenix pusilla</i> Gaertn.	Eenthi	Arecaceae	S	C
<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (L.) Roxb.	Eenthi	Arecaceae	T	C

<i>Phyllanthus acidus</i> (L.)Skeels.	Cheemai nelli	Euphorbiaceae	T	Ex
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schum. & Thonn.	Keela nelli	Euphorbiaceae	H	Ex
<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	Nelli	Euphorbiaceae	T	C
<i>Phyllanthus myrifolices</i> L.		Euphorbiaceae	S	Ex
<i>Phyllanthus polyphyllus</i> Willd.		Euphorbiaceae	T	C
<i>Phyllanthus virgatus</i> G.Forst.		Euphorbiaceae	H	C
<i>Phyllocephalum indicum</i> (Less.)K.Kirkman.		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Physalis angulota</i> L.	Kutti thakkali	Solanaceae	H	C
<i>Pimenta officinalis</i> Lindl.	Sarvasuganthi	Myrtaceae	T	C
<i>Piper betle</i>	Vettilai	Piperaceae	C	Ex
<i>Piper galeatum</i> (Miq.)C.DC.		Piperaceae	C	E
<i>Piper longum</i> L.	Thippili	Piperaceae	S	C
<i>Piper nigrum</i> L.	Milagu	Piperaceae	C	C
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.		Araceae	H	C
<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.)Benth	Kodukkapuli	Caesalpinaceae	T	Ex
<i>Pogonatherum crinitum</i> (Thunb.) Kunth		Poaceae	H	C
<i>Polianthes tuberosa</i> L.		Liliaceae	H	R
<i>Polyalthia fragrans</i> (Dalzell.)Hook.f.&Thomson.	Hemapushpam	Annonaceae	T	E
<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i> (Sonn.)Thwaites.	Ashoka maram	Annonaceae	T	R
<i>Polycarpaea corymbosa</i> (L.)Lam.		Caryophyllaceae	H	C
<i>Polycarpon prostratum</i> (For.)Asc. & Sch.		Caryophyllaceae	H	C
<i>Polygala elongate</i> Klein ex Willd.		Polygallaceae	H	C
<i>Polygala glabra</i> B.Heyne ex A.W.Benn.	Chiriyankai	Polygallaceae	H	C
<i>Polygala javana</i> DC.	Periyankai	Polygallaceae	H	C
<i>Polygonum barbatum</i> L.		Polygonaceae	H	C
<i>Polygonum glabrum</i> Willd.		Polygonaceae	H	C
<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.)Pierre.	Pungu	Fabaceae	T	C
<i>Pothus scandens</i> L.		Araceae	C	C
<i>Pouzolzia zeylanica</i> (L.)Benn.var.alienata		Pouzolziaceae	H	C
<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Perai	Myrtaceae		Ex
<i>Psychotria nigra</i> (Gaertn.)Alston		Rubiaceae	T	C
<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i> L.f	Retha Santhanam	Fabaceae	T	V
<i>Pycnus polystachyos</i> (Rottb.)		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Pycnus punctilatus</i> (Vahl.)Nees.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Pyrus communis</i> L.var.pyraeaster L.	Sabarjelli	Rosaceae	T	Ex
<i>Quisqualis indica</i> L.	Poi Mullai	Combretaceae	T	C
<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> (L.)Benth ex Kurz	Nagavalli	Apocyanaceae	H	E
<i>Rhynchosia minima</i> (L.) DC	Kaattu uzhunthu	Fabaceae	C	C
<i>Rhynchospora corymbosa</i> (L.) Britton.		Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Ricinus commiunis</i> L.	Amanakku	Euphorbiaceae	S	Ex
<i>Rivina humilis</i> L.	Bloodberry	Phytolochiaceae	S	Ex
<i>Ruellia rivularis</i> (Benoist)Bovin ex Benoist.	Pattasuchedi	Acanthaceae	H	C
<i>Ruellia tuberosa</i> L.	Pattasuchedi	Acanthaceae	H	Ex
<i>Salacia fruticosa</i> Heyne ex Lawson.		Celastraceae	C	E
<i>Sansevieria roxburghiana</i> Schult.&Schult.f.		Agavaceae	H	C
<i>Santalum album</i> L.	Santhanam	Fabaceae	T	V
<i>Saraca asoca</i> Rox.	Asoka thetti	Caesalpinaceae	T	E
<i>Sarcostemma viminalis</i> (L.)R.Br.	Somam	Asclepiadaceae	C	C
<i>Schefflera stellata</i> (Gaertn.)Hams		Araliaceae	S	C
<i>Schefflera wallichiana</i> (Wight & Arn.)Hams		Araliaceae	T	E
<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.)Merr.	Poovanam	Sapindaceae	T	C
<i>Schumannianthus virgatus</i> (Roxb.)Rolfe.	Kaatu koovai	Marantaceae	S	C
<i>Scleria lithosperma</i> (L.)Sw.	Vaal pullu	Cyperaceae	H	C
<i>Scorparia dulcis</i> L.	Kallurukki	Scropulariaceae	H	Ex
<i>Scripus supinus</i> (L.) Lye		Cyperaceae	H	R
<i>Sebastiania chamelea</i> (L.)Mull.Arg.	Pei nelli	Euphorbiaceae	H	C
<i>Secamone emetica</i> (Retz.)R.Br.ex Schultes		Asclepiadaceae	C	C
<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> L.	Senkottai	Anacardiaceae	T	C
<i>Semecarpus travancorian</i> Bedd.	Kaattu senkottai	Anacardiaceae	T	E
<i>Sesamum prostratum</i> Retz.	Ellu	Pedaliaceae	H	C
<i>Setaria palmifolia</i> (J.Koenig)Stapf	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Setaria pumila</i> (Poir.)Roem&Schultes	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.Brossum	Vattathirippi	Malvaceae	S	C
<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	Nilathuthi	Malvaceae	H	C
<i>Sida rhombifolia</i> L.	Kurunthotti	Malvaceae	S	C
<i>Smilax zeylanica</i> L.	Karuvilachi	Smilacaceae	C	C
<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Manathakkali	Solanaceae	S	C
<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw.	Chundaikai	Solanaceae	S	Ex
<i>Solanum trilobatum</i> L.	Thoothuvalai	Solanaceae	S	C
<i>Solanum virginianum</i> (L.)	Yanaichundai	Solanaceae	H	C
<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> L.		Asteraceae	H	C

<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (L.) Moench.	Kothumai	Poaceae	H	Ex
<i>Spermacoce hispida</i> L.	Nathachoori	Rubiaceae	H	C
<i>Spermacoce latifolia</i> Aubl.	Taravu chedi	Rubiaceae	H	Ex
<i>Spermacoce remota</i> Lam.	Taravu	Rubiaceae	H	C
<i>Sporobolus indicus</i> (L.) R.Br.	Pullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Stachytarpheta jamaicensis</i> (L.) Vahl		Verbenaceae	H	Ex
<i>Sterculia guttata</i> Roxb.	Kuthirai pidukku	Malvaceae	T	C
<i>Sterculia urens</i> Roxb.var.thorlii(Pierre)		Sterculiaceae	T	C
<i>Streblus asper</i> Lour.	Irumaparuthan	Moraceae	T	C
<i>Strobilanthes ciliatus</i> Nees.	Kurnji	Acanthaceae	S	E
<i>Stropanthus wightianus</i> Wall.ex Wight		Apocyanaceae	S	R
<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L.	Kanjiram	Loganiaceae	T	C
<i>Strychnos potatorum</i> L.f.	Valli kanjiram	Loganiaceae	T	C
<i>Strychnos vanprukii</i> Craib	Kodi Kanjiram	Loganiaceae	C	E
<i>Stylosanthes fruticosa</i> (Retz.)Alston	Vayaruthi pachilai	Fabaceae	S	C
<i>Styrax benzoin</i> Dryand.		Styraceae	T	R
<i>Swietenia maghagoni</i> (L.)Jacq.	Mahakani	Meliaceae	T	Ex
<i>Symplocos cochinchinensis</i> Var.laurina.(Retz.)Noot.		Symplocaceae	T	C
<i>Synedrella nodiflora</i> (L.)Gaertn.	Pachilai	Asteraceae	H	Ex
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (L.)Merr.& L.M.Perry.	Kirampu	Myrtaceae	T	Ex
<i>Syzygium caryophyllatum</i> (L.)Alston.	Cherujarai	Myrtaceae	S	C
<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.)Skeels.var.axillare(Gamble)Sastry & Kashyapa.	Naval	Myrtaceae	T	C
<i>Tabarnaemontana divarica</i> (L.) R.Br	Nanthiarvattam	Apocyanaceae	T	C
<i>Tabarnaemontana gamblei</i> Subr. & A.N.Henry		Apocyanaceae	S	E
<i>Tabarnaemontana heyneana</i> Wall.	Puli nagam palai	Apocyanaceae	T	E
<i>Tagetes patula</i> L.	Mankaipoo chedi	Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Talinum fruticosum</i> (L.)Juss.	Kulampukkerai	Phytolochiaceae	H	C
<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Puli	Fabaceae	T	Ex
<i>Tarenna asiatica</i> (L.)Kutzze ex K.Schum	Akkani palai	Rubiaceae	T	C
<i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.)Kunth.	Tecoma	Bignoniaceae	S	Ex
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.f.	Tekku	Lamiaceae	T	C
<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L.)	Avari	Fabaceae	S	C
<i>Terminalia alata</i> B.Heyne ex Roth tomentosa	Maruthu	Combretaceae	T	C
<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.)Roxb.	Thani	Combretaceae	T	C
<i>Terminalia catapa</i> L.	Vathumai	Combretaceae	T	C
<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Kadukkai	Combretaceae	T	C
<i>Terminalia cuneata</i> Roth.	Maruthu	Combretaceae	T	C
<i>Terminalia paniculata</i> Roth.	Pei kadukkai	Combretaceae	T	C
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Forssk.	Mayirpullu	Poaceae	H	C
<i>Theobroma cacao</i> L.	Coco	Sterculiaceae	T	Ex
<i>Thespesia populnea</i> (L.) Sol.ex Correa.	Poovarasu	Malvaceae	T	C
<i>Thevetia peruviana</i> (Pers.)Merr.	Kattuarali	Apocyanaceae	S	Ex
<i>Thottea siliquosa</i> (Lam.)Ding Hou.	Appama	Aristolochiaceae	S	C
<i>Tiliacora acuminata</i> Miers.		Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.)Miers.	Amirthavalli	Menispermaceae	C	C
<i>Toddalia asiatica</i> (L.)Lam.		Rutaceae	S	C
<i>Tragia hispida</i> Willd.	Choriyan	Euphorbiaceae	H	C
<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.	Charuvellai	Aizoaceae	H	C
<i>Trichomanes plicatum</i> (Bosch) Bedd.		Hymenophyllaceae	H	R
<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Odiyan	Asteraceae	H	Ex
<i>Tylophora fasciculata</i> Buch.-Ham.ex Wight & Arn.		Asclepiadaceae	S	C
<i>Tylophora indica</i> (Burm.f.)Merr.	Nacharuppan	Asclepiadaceae	S	C
<i>Tylophora marcantha</i> Hook.f.		Asclepiadaceae	S	C
<i>Tylophora tetrapetala</i> (Dennst.)Suresh.		Asclepiadaceae	S	C
<i>Utricularia caerulea</i> L.		Lentibulariaceae	H	C
<i>Uvaria naruram</i> (Dunal)Blume.		Annonaceae	C	C
<i>Vateria indica</i> L.		Dipterocarpaceae	T	E
<i>Vernonia anthelmintica</i> (L.)Willd.		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Vernonia cinerea</i> (L.)Less.	Poovankurunthal	Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Vicoa indica</i> (L.)DC.	Mookuthipoovu	Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Vitex altissima</i> L.f.	Ainthalai nochi	Verbanaceae	T	C
<i>Vitex negundo</i> (L.)L.	Karunochi	Verbanaceae	T	C
<i>Vitex trifoliata</i> Merr.	Moovilai Nochi	Verbanaceae	S	C
<i>Waltheria indica</i> L.		Sterculiaceae	H	C
<i>Wattakaka volubilis</i> (L.f.)Stapf.		Asclepiadaceae	S	C
<i>Wedelia chinensis</i> (Osbeck.)Merr.	Palvali chedi	Verbanaceae	H	C
<i>Wedelia trilobata</i> L.	Mookutthipoo	Asteraceae	H	Ex
<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> R.Br.	Venpalai	Apocyanaceae	T	C
<i>Xanthium indicum</i> Koen.		Asteraceae	H	C
<i>Zea mays</i> L.Sp.	Cholam	Poaceae	H	Ex

<i>Zingiber neesatum</i> (J.Graham.)	Inchi	Zingiberaceae	H	R
<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i> Mill.Gard.Dict.	Elanthai	Rhamnaceae	T	C
<i>Ziziphus oenoplia</i> (L.)Mill.	Thodalimullu	Rhamnaceae	C	C
<i>Ziziphus rugosa</i> Lam.	Kattu elanthai	Rhamnaceae	C	C
<i>Zornia diphylla</i> (L.) Pers.		Fabaceae	H	C

Abbreviations: C: Common; Ex: Exotic; E: Endemic; H:Habit; R: Rare; S:Status;T.N: Tamil Name;
V.N: Vernacular; V: Vulnerable.

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